

An Evolutionary Computation based Platform for Optimizing Infrastructure-as-Code Deployment Configurations

Eneko Osaba^{1,2}, Josu Diaz-de-Arcaya¹, Juncal Alonso¹,
Jesus L. Lobo¹, Gorka Benguria¹, and Iñaki Etxaniz¹

¹ TECNALIA, Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA), Spain
eneko.osaba@tecnalia.com,

² Corresponding Author

Abstract. PIACERE is an H2020 European project which objective is to implement a solution involving the development, deployment and operation of Infrastructure-as-Code of applications running on cloud continuum. This technical paper is focused on describing a specific module of the whole PIACERE ecosystem: the *IaC Optimizer Platform*. The main objective of this component is to provide the user with optimized Infrastructure-as-Code configurations deployed on the most appropriate infrastructural elements that best meet the predefined requirements. For properly dealing with this problem, the *IaC Optimizer Platform* is based on Evolutionary Computation metaheuristics. More specifically, it resorts to the well-known NSGA-II and NSGA-III algorithms, depending on the user needs. Additionally, we not only describe the *IaC Optimizer Platform* component in this paper, but we also show how it helps the user to find the most adequate Infrastructure-as-Code configurations.

Keywords: Infrastructure-as-Code, Combinatorial Optimization, Multiobjective Optimization, NSGA-II

1 Introduction

Evolutionary Computation (EC) has emerged as one of the most intensively studied fields within artificial intelligence [1]. The abundant research carried out around EC demonstrates the interest that sparks in the related community, mainly attracted due to the capability and adaptability of EC techniques for efficiently solving a wide-range of high-demanding problems. The renowned flexibility of EC solvers for dealing with both academic-oriented and real-world problems is one of the strengths of EC based meta-heuristics [1]. For this reason, up to now, EC algorithms have been successfully applied to a wide variety of fields, such as medicine [2], energy [3], transportation [4], industry [5, 6], or software engineering [7]. More concretely, the platform presented in this technical paper is framed at the last of these categories: software engineering.

The solution detailed in this paper has been developed in the context of an EU research project, under the programme Horizon 2020. The principal objective of the project, coined as PIACERE³, is to implement a solution involving the development, deployment and operation of Infrastructure-as-Code (IaC, [8]) of applications running on cloud continuum. As part of the whole system, PIACERE has a specific module named as *IaC Optimizer Platform* (IOP, [9]). This paper is focused on describing this concrete module and demonstrating its main advantages and how it contributes to reach the objectives of the whole PIACERE Ecosystem.

In a nutshell, the main goal of the IOP is to provide the user with optimized deployment configurations of the IaC on the most suitable infrastructural elements that best meet the predefined restrictions and requirements. For doing this, the module counts on with a component coined as Infrastructural Elements Catalogue (IEC), where the attributes of all available elements are detailed.

With all this, the motivation of this technical paper is to describe and demonstrate the applicability of the IOP, which is based on EC metaheuristics for dealing with above-described task. For reaching this goal, we describe the main optimization problem to solve, deepening on its particularities and demonstrating its adaptability to the user needs. Also, we detail the developed flexible solving platform, the IOP, which resorts on the Non-dominated Sorted Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II, [10]) and Non-dominated Sorted Genetic Algorithm III (NSGA-III, [11]), depending on user requirements.

The structure of this paper is as follows. In the following section we explain the main optimization problem related with PIACERE and dealt by the IOP. In Section 3, we describe the developed IOP. Then, in Section 4, we present some examples in order to demonstrate the applicability of the implemented platform. We finish this paper with conclusions and further work (Section 5).

2 Optimization of IaC deployment configurations: problem description

In few words, the IOP platform succeeds if it provides the best IaC deployment configurations, optimizing the user introduced objectives and considering all the predefined requirements and constraints. Once the optimization process is finished, the IOP should provide several ranked solutions, clearly showing their main characteristics, so that the user can choose the most appropriate one. Having said that, along this section we describe the main steps for properly defining the optimization problem in PIACERE.

2.1 Introducing the optimization objectives and requirements

An interesting point to highlight here is that the optimization problem dealt in PIACERE is fully defined by the user. First, for performing an optimization,

³ <https://www.piacere-project.eu/>

the IOP should receive an input file from the PIACERE Ecosystem written in an ad-hoc developed modeling language, the PIACERE DevSecOps Modelling Language (DOML⁴). This input file should include an optimization dedicated section, which is the one that defines the optimization problem to solve by the IOP. More specifically, the optimization related section should have the generic form depicted in Figure 1.

```

optimization opt {
  objectives {
  }

  nonfunctional_requirements {
  }
}

```

Fig. 1. Generic form of the optimization section in DOML.

The first part of this section should be devoted to establishing the objectives to optimize. At this moment, three different objectives can be contemplated in the IOP: minimize the cost, and maximize the availability and the performance. Thus, any combination of these objectives can be considered, meaning that the IOP can deem a two-objective and three-objective multi-objective problem to solve, and even single objective problems. The example depicted in Figure 2 shows how the information should be introduced for considering a three-objective multi-objective problem.

```

objectives {
  "cost" => min
  "availability" => max
  "performance" => max
}

```

Fig. 2. Objectives section considering three objectives.

In addition to the optimization objectives, the IOP has been adapted also for considering a set of non-functional requirements. Up to now, and based on the interests expressed by use case owners, five different requirements are contemplated for the IOP:

- Assign a *maximum cost* for the overall configuration.
- Assign a *minimum availability* for the overall configuration.
- Assign a *minimum performance* for the overall configuration.
- *Restrict the region* of the selected elements.

⁴ <https://www.piacere-doml.deib.polimi.it/>

- *Restrict the providers* of the elements.

With all this, we show in Figure 3 an example of the five requirements, and how they should be introduced in the `nonfunctional_requirement` part previously explained:

```

nonfunctional_requirements {
  req1 "Cost <= 200.0" max 200.0 => "cost";
  req2 "Availability >= 98.0%" min 98.0 => "availability";
  req3 "Performance >= 10.0%" min 98.0 => "performance";
  req4 "Region" values "00EU" => "region";
  req5 "Provider" values "AMAZ" => "provider";
}

```

Fig. 3. `nonfunctional_requirement` part considering five different requirements.

As can be seen, cost, availability and performance are introduced as double values, while region and provider features should be defined using string-based keys. As in the case of the objectives, the user is able to choose as many requirements as needed (among the five above defined) to define the use case.

Finally, and regarding the optimization process, the definition of this kind of constraints determines the search space of the optimization algorithm. Once this solution space is defined, the algorithm is run guaranteeing that all solutions provided as output compulsorily meet each and every one of the requirements defined. In other words, solutions that do not meet all constraints will be categorized as unfeasible.

2.2 Introducing the optimization variables

Another important feature to consider when designing the problem is related with the optimization variables that will compose it. At this moment, three different elements are available in the IEC: Virtual Machines (VM), Storages and Data Bases. This means that the IaC deployment configurations will be composed by any combination of these elements. In order for the user to be able to fix the kind and amount of elements needed for the use case, an additional requirement can be contemplated in the `nonfunctional_requirement`, which can be depicted as follows:

```
req1 "elements" => "";}

```

Using this structure, the user is able to feed the combination of elements that is searching for. For example, if the user needs to deploy a service composed of three different VMs and one database, the `elements` part should be:

```
req1 "elements" => "VM, VM, VM, Database";

```

That is, the elements requirement should be introduced as a list of strings. It is important to spotlight here that this combination of elements will define the complexity of the problem, the size of the solutions and, subsequently, the size of the individuals that NSGA-II and NSGA-III will work with.

3 IaC Optimizer Platform

Once the input DOML is received by the IOP, it *i)* retrieves all the information from this input, *ii)* gathers all the information from the IEC, *iii)* builds the optimization problem, and *iv)* calculates the best combination of elements that optimizes the defined objectives, meeting the nonfunctional requirements. For doing this, the IOP relies on the above-mentioned algorithms:

- *Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II* (NSGA-II): this is, arguably, the most renowned algorithm for multi-objective optimization purposes. The NSGA-II consists of a generational genetic algorithm which resorts to a Pareto ranking scheme to enhance the convergence. Furthermore, NSGA-II method uses the crowding distance density estimator for ensuring the diversity on the Pareto front. In the context of the IOP, the NSGA-II algorithm is employed for solving both single-objective and two-objective multi-objective problems.
- *Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm III* (NSGA-III): this method is an evolution of the above mentioned one, which follows a similar structure. The NSGA-III, which is used in the IOP for dealing with the three-objective multi-objective problems, replaces the crowding distance operator used in NSGA-II with a clustering operator aided by a group of well-distributed reference points.

We introduce now a simplified example with the main objective of properly describing how EC meta-heuristics are adapted to solve the problem detailed in Section 2. This way, let us assume an IEC composed of **Storage**, **Database** and **VM** type elements. Furthermore, for each of these elements, let us assume five different options, forming the following simplified IEC:

- **Storage**: [St_Europe, St_Spain, AZ_2, G_2, St_Spain, St_USA]
- **Database**: [mysql.GB, db.dyn, postgresSQL.GR, r4.larg, m3.med]
- **VM**: [C1France, C2Europe, m5.large, t2.nano, DS13v2]

Additionally, each of these elements has a set of attributes assigned regarding its cost, provider, expected availability or region. Furthermore, let us assume that a user has introduced as input the real-world based DOML depicted in Figure 4.

Meaning that the IOP should find the best combination contemplating one storage, one database and three VM, while optimizing the cost, the availability, and the performance. Moreover, the solutions offered by the IOP must not exceed a total cost of 100 Euros, the expected availability must be higher than a 98%, and the region of the chosen elements must be Europe (00EU).

Based on this example, the NSGA-III, in this case, could define a tentative solution using the following codification: [0, 2, 3, 1, 0]: [195.5, 99.5, 10]. It should be pointed here that a solution is codified as a list of indexes of the elements in the IEC. Thus, considering that the combination to find is [**Storage**, **Database**, **VM**, **VM**, **VM**], the solution [0, 2, 3, 1, 0] represents [St_Europe,

```

optimization opt {
  objectives {
    "cost" => min
    "availability" => max
    "performance" => max
  }
  nonfunctional_requirements {
    req1 "Cost <= 100.0" max 100.0 => "cost";
    req2 "Availability >= 98.0%" min 98.0 => "availability";
    req3 "Region values "00EU" => "region";
    req4 "elements" => "Storage, DB, VM, VM, VM";
  }
}

```

Fig. 4. Example of an input DOML, based on a real case.

postgreSQL.GR, t2.nano, C2Europe, C1France]. Furthermore, the associated objective values of this solutions would be [195.5, 99.5, 10], depicting a cost equal to 195.5 Euros, an availability of 99.5% and a performance metric of 10.

4 Applicability demonstration

At this point, it is important to highlight here that the IOP has been implemented in JAVA programming language, and that both NSGA-II and NSGA-III have been implemented using the jMetal framework [12]. It is also interesting to mention that the choosing of NSGA-II and NSGA-III has been conducted as a result of an experimentation using additional similar methods such as the SPEA2 [13], MOCell [14] or MOMBI [15], among many others. This experimentation has demonstrated that for the planned uses cases, NSGA-II and NSGA-III are excellent choices in terms of computation effort and results quality. Furthermore, we depict in Table 1 the parameterization used for these techniques, which is the same for both of them. These settings have been selected after carrying out an extensive empirical analysis.

NSGA-II & NSGA-III	
Parameter	Value
Crossover Probability	90%
Crossover Distribution Index	20
Crossover Function	Integer simulated binary crossover [16]
Mutation Probability	10%
Mutation Distribution Index	20
Mutation Function	Integer Polynomial Mutation [17]
Maximum of Evaluations	10K
Population Size	100

Table 1. Parameter values for NSGA-II and NSGA-III.

Having said that, we present in this section a real-world example addressed by the IOP. For this test, an IEC composed of 49 elements has been used: 10 Databases, 7 Storages and 32 Virtual Machines. In this example, a three-objective problem was faced. The input DOML was the same as represented in Figure 4.

Once this input DOML was received by the IOP, it conducted the optimization through the application of NSGA-III. After the completion of the optimization process, the IOP returns the solutions found using also the DOML modeling language. To do that, the IOP enriches the input DOML extending it with all the information referred to the optimization. In this specific example, the IOP found three solutions, which were returned as depicted in Figure 5.

```

optimization opt {
  objectives {
    "cost" => min
    "availability" => max
    "performance" => max
  }
  nonfunctional_requirements {
    req1 "Cost <= 100.0" max 100.0 => "cost";
    req2 "Availability >= 98.0%" min 98.0 => "availability";
    req3 "Region" values "00EU" => "region";
    req4 "elements" => "Storage, DB, VM, VM, VM";
  }
  solution sol2 {
    objectives {
      cost 75.53 euro
      availability 98.82000000000001 %
      performance 26.0 metric
    }
    decisions ["[Storage1_Spain, db.dynamo.3, m1.tiny, t2.nano, m1.small]"]
  }
  solution sol3 {
    objectives {
      cost 84.53 euro
      availability 98.88 %
      performance 24.0 metric
    }
    decisions ["[Storage4_Europe, db.dynamo.3, m1.tiny, t2.nano, m1.small]"]
  }
  solution sol4 {
    objectives {
      cost 95.53 euro
      availability 98.92 %
      performance 25.0 metric
    }
    decisions ["[Storage1_Spain, db.dynamo.3, m1.tiny, t2.nano, m1.medium]"]
  }
}

```

Fig. 5. Results for the two objective use case.

For each of these solutions, the value of each objective is depicted in the section **objectives** of each solution, while the elements chosen for the deployment are listed in the **decisions** part. Lastly, the IOP introduces the features of each found solution in the **concretizations** part of the DOML. For the sake of space limitations, we represent in Figure 6 just an excerpt of a specific solutions (*sol3* in Figure 5).

```

concrete_infrastructure con_infra3{
  provider openstack {
    storage Storage4_Europe {
      properties {
        st_flavor = "Storage4_Europe";
        st_name = "Storage4_Europe";
        st_Availability = 99.8;
        st_Cost_Currency = 15;
        st_Request_Response_time_Storage_Performance = 3;
        st_Region = "00EU";
        st_Storage_Subtype = "BLOK";
        st_Storage_Capacity = 100;
        st_Storage_Type = "GENE";
        st_provider_OU = "ARSY";
        st_Storage_Data_Redundancy = "ZONS";
      }
    }
  }
  dbms db_dynamo_3 {
    properties {
      db_flavor = "db_dynamo_3";
      db_name = "db_dynamo_3";
      db_Availability = 99.6;
      db_Database_Technology = "AMNR";
      db_Data_Transfer_OUT = 35;
      db_Zone = "DEEU";
      db_Virtual_CPU_Cores = 2;
      db_Data_Transfer_IN = 35;
      db_Database_Storage_Capacity = 100;
      db_provider_OU = "AMAZ";
      db_Database_Type = "00NR";
      db_Transaction_Unit_DTU_Database_Performance = 3;
      db_Cost_Currency = 35;
      db_Region = "00EU";
    }
  }
  vm m1_tiny{
    properties {
      vm_flavor = "m1_tiny";
      vm_name = "m1_tiny";
      vm_Availability = 98;
      vm_Response_time_Virtual_Machine_Performance = 10;
      vm_Zone = "SPEU";
      vm_Memory = 512;
      vm_Frequency_per_Core = 1500;
      vm_Virtual_CPU_Cores = 1;
      vm_provider_OU = "OPEN";
      vm_public_IP_type = "IPV4";
      vm_Cost_Currency = 10;
      vm_Region = "00EU";
      vm_Instance_Storage = 1;
    }
  }
}

```

Fig. 6. An excerpt of how the IOP concretizes the results in the output DOML.

Furthermore, the IOP ranks the different deployment configurations found using one of the optimization objectives as reference. In this sense, and in order to do it flexible enough, the IOP adapts itself to the needs of the user, who can define which is the objective considered as reference. For doing that, the input DOML is used. More concretely, the `objectives` part of the `optimization opt` section of the DOML is used, deeming the first value as reference objective. In the example above defined, and as can be seen in Figure 5, the reference objective

is the **Cost**. For this reason, returned solutions are ordered using this criterion (starting from the cheapest solutions, and finishing with most expensive one).

5 Conclusions

PIACERE is an H2020 European project whose objective is to implement a solution involving the development, deployment and operation of Infrastructure-as-Code of applications running on cloud continuum. In this context, this technical paper has been focused on describing a specific module of the whole PIACERE ecosystem, coined as IOP, which main goal is to provide the user with the optimized deployment configurations of the IaC on the most suitable infrastructural elements that best meet the predefined restrictions and requirements.

For reaching its objectives and dealing with the above-described task, the IOP is based on EC metaheuristics. More concretely, the IOP resorts to the well-known NSGA-II and NSGA-III algorithms, depending on the user needs. Furthermore, in this paper, we have not only described the IOP component, but we have also shown how it works and how it helps the user to find optimized IaC configurations.

As future work, the evolution of the IOP has been planned, having as a short-term objective the adaptation to additional real-world oriented use cases, by introducing further objectives and requirements. As long-term objective, the development of more sophisticated versions of both the NSGA-II and NSGA-III will be conducted.

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